

Appendix A - Related Works

Title	Authors	Year	SOBM Concepts Used
Exploring business models for sustainability: A bibliographic investigation of the literature and future research directions	Preghenella et al.	2021	business models for sustainability
Sustainable Business Models: Literature Review of Main Contributions and Themes	Silvia and Truzzi	2020	sustainable business models, business models for sustainability, triple layered business model
Business models for environmental sustainability: Contemporary shortcomings and some perspectives	De Giacomo and Bleischwitz	2020	business models for environmental sustainability
Sustainable Business Models: A Review	Nosratabadi et al.	2019	sustainable business model
Sustainable business model innovation: A review	Geissdoerfer et al.	2018	business model, business model innovation, sustainable business model, circular business model, business model for sustainability
Embracing the variety of sustainable business models: A prolific field of research and a future research agenda	Dentchev et al	2018	sustainable business models, lean and green models, circular business model, social entrepreneurship, sustainable entrepreneurship, sustainable innovations
Business Model Innovation for Sustainability: Towards a Unified Perspective for Creation of Sustainable Business Models	Evans et al	2017	business model for sustainability, sustainable business model
Business Models for Sustainability: Origins, Present Research, and Future Avenues	Schaltegger et al	2016	sustainable business model, sustainability-oriented business mode, business model for sustainability